

A NEW PHILOSOPHICAL PARADIGM OF EUROPEAN BORDERS: NONLINEAR DYNAMICS

Abstract

Do borders exist in philosophy? We believe that philosophy has no borders and that geographical, social, and colloquial differences in philosophy are only provisional aspects. Firstly, the philosophy's main point and virtue are the principles of universality and generality. Secondly, claims to a “bordered” dimension in philosophy, - termed by Derrida as “philosophical nationalism” - reduce philosophical thinking to a worldview and ideology. Thirdly, philosophy acquires its borderless dimension through critique as a preposition for the constant transfer beyond and across different borders, including the boundaries of different theoretical constructions. At the same time, borders as a phenomenon have always been the object of philosophical enquiry through their genesis, functions, and qualities such as connectedness and separateness, situatedness and spatialization. Another reason is the close connection between the meanings of space and territory. It is not coincidence that the key dichotomy of deterritorialization and reterritorialization, in the thought of Gilles Deleuze and Felix Guattari, emerged from within their philosophy of immanence and only later were adopted in the vocabulary of geography and geopolitics.

Philosophical analysis has become crucial for understanding the new processes and events that have emerged and developed over the last ten years on the European borders. The purpose of this article is to highlight the visible parameters of the new philosophical paradigm concerning European borders. Every new philosophical paradigm, including European borders, need a qualitative move. Braidotti suggests some qualitative criteria for paradigmatic shift:

”supra-disciplinarity, meta-discursivity, material grounding, nomadic generative force and affirmative ethics”. It includes such practices as “cartographic accuracy, with the corollary of ethical accountability, non-linearity, the powers of memory and the imagination and the strategy of de-familiarization” (Braidotti, 2013).

The essence of borders is quite ambiguous. They can be spatial, such as geographical, national, cultural, ethnic, or linguistic, and they can be based on constructions of identity. Our task to highlight these “new tools” for explaining the contemporary migration situation, bearing in mind that crossing European borders can involve not only moving from one location to another but also navigating intermediate spaces.

The need for more pluralistic or sometimes alternative views of the role of borders in postmodern life became evident. N. Vaughan-Williams finds that the above meaning “offers significant, yet untapped, implications for analysing borders across a global bio-political terrain” (Vaughan-Williams 2009: 733). Researchers advocate for a new lexicon and an innovative framework regarding

borders and migration. This lexicon should be anchored in significant ideas from Foucault and Agamben, such as “to move from a geopolitical to a biopolitical horizon of thinking”, *deterritorialization and reterritorialization* (Deleuze and Guattari), the new materialism such notions such as *diffraction* and *the positivity of affirmation* (Rosi Braidotti and Karen Barad), *nonlinear dynamics* (Donna J. Haraway), *materialization/dematerialization of border* (Élisabeth Vallet, Sarah Green, Olga Demetriou).

My paper aims to explore the complexities of European borders and migration primarily from the perspective of new materialism, emphasizing the intricate connections that link bordering processes through the past, present, and future. A new materialist interpretation of diffraction challenges the idea that the crisis is merely a linear outcome of policy failures. “We can understand diffraction patterns – as patterns of difference that make a difference – to be the fundamental constituents that make up the world”. (Barad, 2007: 72)

In this vein, it is appropriate to use another notion developed by Rosi Braidotti that “indicates the process of transmuted negative passions into productive and sustainable praxis... which does not deny horror and violence”. (Braidotti 2016: 51). For Braidotti, the positivity of affirmation is the desire to express constitutive freedom which is conducive to ethical behavior. This idea bridges the gap between pragmatism and a humanitarian approach by supporting the latter in current events. This diffractive approach portrays the situation of borders as a complex pattern of obstacles that reshape our understanding of both the past and the present. In this context, diffraction refers to the evolving nature of borders, including physical barriers, such as fences, and invisible phantom borders that symbolize memories. The concept of phantom borders illustrates how the remnants of old borders affect contemporary life, especially during mass migrations, resulting in a dual and nostalgic reality.

This approach facilitates a deeper examination of borders and borderlands, allowing us to understand them through the dimensions of space and time. Rather than being fixed lines on a map, it argues that borders are dynamic and fluid arenas, shaped by the constantly changing political landscapes, particularly in the condition of mass migration. The significance of external borders, particularly in Eastern Europe, is undergoing a profound transformation, becoming increasingly complex and varied. This rapid change in border dynamics means we must view borders as a changeable process not just as simple demarcations.

The phrase nonlinear dynamics of European borders highlights the complex and evolving nature of borders across Europe. It indicates that their characteristics change in response to globalization, digitalization, and geopolitization. These borders oscillate between periods of openness and restriction; they are shaped by European integration and technological advancements.

The philosophy of Deleuze and Guattari challenges traditional ideas about territory, identity, and power. They introduce the concept of deterritorialization, which offers a valuable framework for understanding the evolving relationships between individuals and territories. Deterritorialization encompasses two key

phenomena: de-bordering and re-bordering. De-bordering involves to the gradual reduction or elimination of borders, as exemplified by the Schengen Area. Conversely, re-bordering involves the re-establishment or strengthening of borders, frequently in response to events like mass migration, war, or pandemics. These nonlinear dynamics highlight the contradictory nature of European borders, demonstrating the connectivity and division.

Recent events in Europe, such as mass migration, the pandemic, the closure of national borders, hybrid migration and contrabands patterns, and Russia's war against Ukraine, clearly illustrate that the concept of borders is undergoing a significant transformation. Brian Massumi describes our current experience as both a continuous state of exception and a paradigmatic shift where "what once provided stability is perpetually shifting into crisis." He suggests that we are living in "a very unstable, quasi-chaotic situation," where the complexity of interlocking systems undermines the very foundations upon which we rely for stability (Massumi, 2012).

Our task is to represent borders as dispersed, "transitional" practices that require a theoretical framework and a moral evaluation and an axiological perspective. This ultimately results in a scenario where biopolitical security and dehumanization are transforming the hierarchy of European values in public discourse.

The term materialization of a border describes the process by which an abstract concept of a border becomes a concrete, physical presence. This often involves the construction of imposing barriers, fences, walls, or other structures that clearly separate one area from another. Such boundaries do not merely mark geographic separations; they carry profound socio-political implications that deeply impact communities, economies, and ecosystems. The materialization of a border encompasses not only barriers but also an increase in border controls.

In essence, the materialization of a border reflects the evolution of invisible lines on maps into tangible forms with which citizens interact daily. The physical attributes of these borders serve as material identifiers, assessed through various parameters, including biometric data and personal documentation. This meticulous examination delves into the complexities surrounding border management and immigration processes, shedding light on various challenges individuals face when crossing these thresholds. Furthermore, the increasing use of borders as instruments of control provides a critical opportunity to evaluate individuals' rights to cross these boundaries objectively. Yet, the reality is that border crossing points and the borders themselves often become flashpoints of conflict, where tensions escalate and confrontations arise, highlighting the profound challenges associated with enforcement of such divisions. The manifestation of a border illustrates how its physical characteristics function as tangible markers of identity, influenced by a multitude of parameters. These borders delineate not only geographical boundaries but also embody cultural, historical, and social significances that give them their unique identities.

In conclusion, it is necessary to remember that when we talk about borders, we are talking not only about the laws and rules of the game. state interests and security, but also about the fates of a huge number of people who have found themselves drawn into a cycle of non-linear circumstances and the contradictory nature of the

very functioning of borders. Overcoming the contradiction between security and humanity is one of the important tasks of philosophical analysis when we speak about migration. Ukraine's long-suffering borders are an example of all the above definitions of border violations and illegal border demarcation and its phantomization.

The war in Ukraine began primarily with the violation of the state border. The facts of such violations undermine the political status quo of Europe.

Keywords: border, deterritorialization, materialization of a border, nonlinear dynamics.

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